

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Contribution of IR crosses to improved cultivars for irrigated rice in Latin America

Federico Cuevas-Pérez, IRRI liaison scientist for Latin America, Apartado Aéreo 6713, Cali, Colombia

Adoption of modern semidwarf rice varieties in Latin America began in the late 1960s with the introduction of IR8. Although yield gains were impressive, grain quality was below regional standards. This stimulated additional introductions and breeding work to select locally adapted materials.

After nearly 20 yr of germplasm improvement work, modern semidwarf varieties are planted on 31 % of the rice area and contribute 56% of total Latin American rice production. For irrigated rice, 80% of the area and production are modern varieties. International collaboration through the International Network for the Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER, formerly IRTP) has been a major force behind these technological improvements.

To determine the contribution of IR materials to the improvement of irrigated rice in Latin America, the pedigrees of 143 cultivars released 1971-89 were ana-

lyzed: 85% had at least one IR line in their parentage.

Chile was the only country with no cultivar showing IR parentage, probably because of subtropical growing conditions. Other countries whose materials had low IR input were the traditional exporters, Surinam and Uruguay.

Table 1. IR breeding lines in the parentage of irrigated rice cultivars released in Latin America, 1971-89.

IR line	Cultivar name	Country, year of release
IR442	Huallaga	Peru, 1972
	BR2	Brazil, 1978
IR579	IR100	Nicaragua, 1973
	INIAP2	Ecuador, 1971
	Navolato A7 1	Mexico, 1971
IR665	IR665	Brazil, 1976
IR822	CR1113	Costa Rica, 1974
IR837	Bamoa A75	Mexico, 1975
	Piedras Negras A74	Mexico, 1974
IR841	IR841	Brazil, 1974
	EMPASC 104	Brazil, 1985
IR930	BR-IRGA 408	Brazil, 1975
	Chancay	Peru, 1972
	Cica 4	Colombia, 1971
	INIAP6	Ecuador, 1972
	Naylamp	Peru, 1971
IR1055	N	Guyana, 1975
IR1529	IR1529	Cuba, 1978
IR2058	Pesagro 102	Brazil, 1983
IR2153	Juma 62	Dominican Republic, 1986
IR4570	PA-3	Peru, 1984
IR5853	Saavedra	Bolivia, 1987
IR8208	Pesagro 101	Brazil, 1983
IR18348	INIAP11	Ecuador, 1989

In rice varieties from the rest of the region, 24 cultivars were direct selections of IR lines (Table 1). About two-thirds of them were released 1971-78. IR930 was named in five countries. Navolato A71 (IR579) in Mexico and INIAP II (IR18348) in Ecuador are the most widely grown direct IR selections. Since 1978, most of the IR line contributions have been as parents in local crosses.

Fifty-two IR lines have been used in national breeding programs; the most frequently found were IR8, IR579, and IR930 (Table 2). Some 90% of the 2.1 million ha of irrigated favorable rainfed rice area of Latin America is currently planted to cultivars with IR8 in their parentage. □

Table 2. IR lines most frequently found in the parentage of Latin American irrigated rice cultivars, 1971-89.

IR line	Progenitor of released cultivars	Genetic contribution per cultivar ^a	
		Mean	Maximum
IR8	76.2	0.36	0.75
IR262	26.6	0.50	0.50
IR579	36.4	0.29	1.00
IR661	9.1	0.22	0.50
IR665	34.3	0.28	1.00
IR841	16.8	0.17	1.00
IR930	51.0	0.38	1.00

^a Assuming 50% contribution of each parent in a single cross. A contribution of 1.0 indicates that the IR line was released as a cultivar.

Breeding methods—hybrid rice

Photosynthesis and respiration in rice hybrids

K. S. Murty and S. K. Dey, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Heterosis in photosynthesis in F₁ rice hybrids is not well established; it is considered to be mostly cross-specific. We studied heterosis in photosynthetic rate (Pn) and maintenance respiration (L_{MR}) in IR54152 A/IR54 and V20 A/

IR36 at the vegetative (35 d after planting) and flowering stages during the 1990 dry season. MR provides energy for the biochemical and physiological state of established tissues. It differs considerably among cultivars.

The hybrids, their restorers, and check variety Swarnaprabha were planted in pots. Pn in the second leaf at the vegetative stage and in the flag leaf at flowering were measured by LI-6000 at full sunlight (about 1200 μE/m² per s). MR was

measured by differential respirometer as CO₂ evolution rate on excised leaves after incubation in the dark for 8 h.

The hybrids showed higher Pn and MR than their restorers at both growth stages (see table). Pn was similar, but MR was higher in the hybrid with IR36 than in the hybrid with IR54. Both hybrids had higher Pn and MR than Swarnaprabha.

Heterosis over restorer was consistently higher in V20 A/IR36. Heterosis for Pn was higher at the vegetative stage than at flowering; differences in heterosis for MR were only marginal. Standard